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Review Article

A Review Of Smart Nanobot-Based Medication Delivery Methods For Cancer Treatment

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ABSTRACT

One of the most deadly illnesses of the twenty-first century is cancer. Chemotherapy and radiation therapy are excruciating procedures that include the use of numerous medications, such as antitumor antibiotics, which have numerous adverse effects. As a substitute, DNA nanorobots are a promising cancer treatment method that functions precisely and is far safer than conventional therapies. According to reports, DNA nanobots will mark a significant advancement in medical research. This bot's main goal is to locate and eradicate cancer cells from the human body. One strand of DNA makes up these bots. folded into the form you like. There will be two modes for the bots: "off," where the clamshells are securely closed to avoid damaging cells without any damage and a "on" position, in which the clamshell opens to let the medication reach the malignant cells, allowing the medication to remove the malignant cell. Once this new concept passes its initial human test, it will be widely adopted by the general population. In this review, we concentrate on cancer eradication. cell. As a secondary objective, the bot can be used to treat any other disease because it can be programmed and has the capacity to carry a payload. Nanobot development is already underway and might be available to the general public in around five years.

INTRODUCTION

A summary of cancer:

Over the years, cancer has shown to be a devastating and painful disease. It is a recognized truth that an increasing number of individuals are, in a sense, being infected with this terrible illness. Hippocrates (460–370 B.C.) is credited with coining the word cancer, although he was not the

first to define the disease. The word comes from the Greek word karkinos, which means "tumor." "The primary cause of cancer, according to him, was an imbalance between the four humors. Previous research on mummies which goes as far back as 1600 BC—has revealed signs of cancer cells in human bones. In 1.9 million new cases of cancer, of which 600,000 were diagnosed in 2023,

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according to the reports indicated. Any disease that can damage a person's entire body, without respect to substantial discrimination, is commonly referred to as cancer. Neoplasms and malignant tumors are the synonyms for it. To put it simply, it can be defined as the abnormal proliferation of cells in various human body parts that spreads to other tissues and eventually organs in an attempt to destroy the entire organ system; this process is known as metastasis. Lung cancer is caused by unchecked cell division in the lungs. The typical role of cells in our bodies is to divide and produce an abundance of copies; however, for various reasons, the cells in our lungs undergo mutations that lead to the production of additional copies.

Stages of cancer

A cancer in **stage 1** is often tiny and contained in the organ in which it originated. In most cases, **stage 2** indicates that although the tumor has grown larger than in stage 1, the cancer has not yet begun to spread to the surrounding tissues.

stage 3 can occasionally indicate that cancer cells have invaded nearby lymph nodes. Depending on the specific kind of cancer,

Stage 4

Typically indicates a more advanced malignancy. There are cancer cells in the adjacent lymph nodes, and it might have begun to expand into the surrounding tissues.

Stage 5

denotes the progression of the cancer to an additional organ within the body. to the lung or liver, for instance. Another name for this is metastatic or secondary cancer.

Death statergy of cancer

The cancer incidence from 28 Population-Based Cancer Registries (PBCRs) for the years 2012–2016 was reported in the National Cancer Registry Programme Report 2020. This served as the foundation for estimating the incidence of cancer in India. To estimate the age-sex stratified

population, data about the population at risk was taken from the Indian Census (2001 and 2011). The country's States and regions were assigned to PBCRs in order to better understand the epidemiology of cancer. To calculate the number of cancer cases in India for 2022, the age-specific incidence rate for each distinct anatomical site of cancer was applied to the estimated population.

Nanoboats

Introduction of nanorobots, which enable the performance of a variety of medical procedures and the access An artificially created device that can freely diffuse throughout the human body and interact molecularly with particular cells is known as a nanorobot. Nanomedicines are meant to treat and prevent diseases, preserve and improve human health using instruments at the nanomolecular size and biological nanomolecular knowledge of the due to their high potential for research and possible applications in the treatment of cancers . One of the most promising uses

Various Nanoboats Types

Pharmacy Technician: The pharyocyte is a one to two micrometer nanorobot. Based on the demands of the assignment, the cargo kept in the nanorobotics' onboard tanks system is able to be released into the nearby additional cellular fluid or given straight into the cytosol utilizing a transmembrane injector mechanism 9.

Respiocyte: Man-made Oxygen Transporter nanobot. The energy source is internal. bloodsugar. The capacity of this artificial cell is 236 times greater. more oxygen to the tissues per volume unit than red blood cells (Cells of red blood).

It is an oblate spheroidal device for **microbivores**. Applications of 3.4 μm diameter nanomedicine has a diameter of 2.0 μm along its primary axis its smaller axis. The little robot can eat as much as 200pW. This ability is employed to break down stuck microorganisms.

Clottocytes are a particular class of nanorobot that has a distinct biological ability: Typically, they produce chemicals that support coagulation 10

Chromalloyte: This cell would take the place of complete chromosomes in each cell, so correcting hereditary illnesses' consequences and other caused harm to our genes over time, blocking growing older. This will initially assess the circumstances inside a cell by looking through the contents and activity of the cell after that Working molecule by molecule and structure by structure, it will be able to take action. to fix the entire cell

Nanorobot components: the substructures in Ananorobot consists of 11–12

Payload: This empty space contains a little dosage of medication or medications. It is able to move over the blood as well as motion and For mobility, use mechanical legs or manipulator arms. The program created for them is called Control Design. modeling nanorobots in a setting with fluids in which Brownian motion is predominant. Chemical sensors on the nanorobots allow them to identify the target chemical compounds. The three primary swarm kinds Ant colonies are used as intelligence

tools. artificial bee colony (ABC), optimization (ACO),and PSO (16 particle swarm optimization) Its structural component has been molecular sorting. fins, rotor, nano sensors, and propellers. Bio-Nanorobots: artificial nanobots created byutilizing b's properties of biological materials' structures and functions, such as DNA and peptides. These are influenced by more than just both by technology and by nature

Perfect Features for Nanorobots

- 1.They should have pieces between 1 and 100 nm in size and fall between 0.5 and 3 microns; otherwise, they may obstruct capillary flow:
- 2 .Nanorobots have a passive, diamond-shaped shell that shields them from immune system attacks.
- 3.It can encode messages to be heard by the doctor in order to communicate with them. transmissions at carrier wave frequencies between 1 and 100 MHz.,4. It has the ability to replicate itself numerous times, a function known as self replication 3, to replace worn-out units. of nanomedicines is the development of hard-to-reach bodily areas .

Construction of nanobots:

created DNA-based nanobots that transport medications to treat cancer. When injected into the body, these bots specifically destroy malignant cells. These automata are not larger than a

red blood cell by 200 times and have a diameter of just 35 nm.The researchers utilized Cadnano, an open-source program, to develop the nanorobots' structural layout . They then used DNA origami to construct the bots. The process of creating small,

structured structures out of is referred to as DNA origami. One can construct DNA into a desired form by chopping off a tiny piece (the staple strand) and affixing it to a lengthy string. matching base pairs to create the required shape. shows how the bot was designed and put together. These bots have the appearance of a nanoscale, two-half, open-ended barrel that can be opened and closed like a clamshell. Each of the two parts is joined by molecules joined by molecular locks, latches and hinges. composed of two helices of DNA. There are 12 in the botnet. locations on payload molecules. Externally, there are two locations where aptamers, which are small nucleotide strands having unique patterns for identifying chemicals on the intended cell placed within the nanobot and held in place by molecular anchors. When the aptamers identify their target, they function as clasps, and the apparatus opens up to release the payload. The nanobots are designed to operate in two modes: ON and OFF. After identifying a target cell by analyzing its surface proteins, the two split in half, releasing the medication to that specific cell (on location). When they're off, they're firmly shut

working of nanoboats

A logic gate encoded with aptamers governs the nanobots. Any kind of nanoparticle can be engineered to function as an independent biocomputing device that can perform Boolean logic gates (NAND, NOT, AND, and OR. Given that DNA is an organic substrate for computation, it has benefited robots and a wide range of logic circuits [34]. DNA includes the logic-gating functionality, and the logic-gating is accomplished by means of input-induced dismantling of the structures in the genetic material. Various types of DNA-based biocomputing have previously to be. It's now demonstrated that DNA origami can be employed to design tiny robots with interactive

capabilities when inserted into the body, they interact dynamically with one another.

Working Methodology Of Nanobots The nanobots are controlled by an aptamer-encoded logic gate [41]. Any type of nanoparticle can be transformed into autonomous biocomputing structures that are capable of executing Boolean logic gates (NAND, NOT, AND, and OR). Since DNA is a natural substrate for computing, it has benefitted a diverse set of logic circuits and robotics [34]. The logic gating functionality is incorporated into the DNA, and the logic gating is achieved through input-induced disassembly of the structures in the DNA [42]. Different forms of DNA-based biocomputing have already been demonstrated. Now, it has been shown that DNA origami can be used to devise nanoscale robots which have the capacity to interact with each other with dynamism when introduced into the body. These interactions produce logical outputs, which are used to open or close the nanobot to release the drug, on spotting the target cell. The ON and OFF positions of nanobots are depicted in Fig. 3.

Preliminary Trials On Nanobots And Its Mechanism

Components of nanoboats

Despite the fact that nanobots come in a variety of forms, we'll look at the essential and fundamental parts of medical nanobots. Shells, Propellers, Power Sources, Nano cameras, payloads, Sensors, Lasers, Actuators, and Communicators will be the components that will be addressed here

shell

A nanorobot's shell is its external body. Because of the way they are made, human cells can absorb them. A variety of materials can be used to make them. Materials including silica, carbon, and diamond are frequently used. Noteworthy is the fact that these shells play a critical role in an individual's safety. It should be planned for in order to reduce the possibility of harming the cells,

tissues, and organs as well as the potential reactions between the components.

propeller

It is a part that powers the nanorobots inside the human body, just as the name would imply. The primary function of the propellers is to facilitate the nanobots' bloodstream movement. A swimming tail on a nanobot functions nearly like a propeller to enter the body and pushes against blood flow in a human body. A nanobot can move forward using a variety of propulsion techniques, such as chemical, hydrophilic, magnetic, and so forth.

Power source

These are the outside sources of nanobots that are employed in their operation. Stated differently, they might be viewed as the energy source that powers the nanobots. These sources could come from batteries, hydrogen fuels, nanomotors, and engines, among other things.[When applied to the human body, the power source should be closely observed since it has the potential to significantly affect a person's performance, safety, and overall well-being.

nano camera

The tiny, microscopic cameras known as nano cameras are affixed to the nanobots. The nanocamerarecords live images of navigational pathways and uses that information to guide the nanobots within the human body as they pass through the bloodstreams of their targets. In essence, they serve as a navigational guide.

Payloads

Nanobot payloads are the main purposes for which a nanobot is created or engineered.[45] A study by Douglas and colleagues shows how the payloads in molecular nanobots operate precisely.[63] All in all, this one can demonstrate payloads in nanobots as components or segments of nanobots that are especially built or planned to reach a specific destination and perform the function assigned to it by its operator.

Senser

They are the sensory devices of nanobots. Those sensors that use a nanoscale dimension, for operations are coined as nanosensors. They sense the changes in temperature, changes in alkaline levels, give an insight into cysts or metastasis inside the body of an individual, and so on. Sensors are placed inside the shells and the quantity of biosensors used depends on the functions assigned to it. Organic biosensors are also used to detect the targets and hence analyze them, using biological reactions.

Laser

Lasers are bound to produce high-precision light beams that can penetrate any part of the human body, with medical advancements showing their illustrations in different medical disciplines.[65] In a nanobot, lasers are fabricated and confined to the nanoscale.[66] They are used to blaze harmful materials inside the body, such as blood clots, cancer cells, and so on.[54,66,67] Actuators Actuators are devices that switch that help the nanobots to interact with the body[45] physically. Hence, a nanobot could be placed on the shells, so that, it simplifies the release of drugs, in case of drug delivery. Actuators are an important part of nanobots, as they could be used for multiple techniques such as drug delivery, cell targeting, and so on. In a study done by Actuators are devices that switch that help the nanobots to interact with the body physically. Hence, a nanobot could be placed on the shells, so that, it simplifies the release of drugs, in case of drug delivery. Actuators are an important part of nanobots, as they could be used for multiple techniques such as drug delivery, cell targeting, and so on. In a study done by S Zhao et al., they came to infer that actuators of nanobots play a significant role in surgeries. Communicators Communication with the nanobots, that are introduced into the human body is very much needed to understand the changes and interactions

happening inside the body of an individual. The pre-assigned tasks of the nanobots will be carried out using different

Using nanomaterials in cancer treatment

Supplementary (23-24) lists a number of well-researched nanoparticles. Polymeric nanoparticles (PNPs) with a size range of 10 to 1000 nm can be used to distribute and release chemical medicines to specific locations in a sustainable manner. Polymethyl methacrylate and polyacrylates, two non-biodegradable polymers, were originally used to create nanoparticles, but these materials have changed over the past few decades. One difficulty with employing these kinds of PNPs is their timely removal because they produce toxicity and persistent inflammation. Biodegradable polymers, which vary in their structures and properties, have been developed to address this challenge. These include polylactic acid, poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid), and poly (amino acids). These polymers demonstrate outstanding advantages. Pharmaceutical grade PNPs enhance loading capacity, boost stability, and shield medicines against deterioration. Metal nanomaterials, however, are not taken into consideration. In cancer treatment, medication distribution is crucial, and non-conjugated polymers with intrinsic luminescence have a unique advantage in this regard. Both passive and active targeting are included in drug delivery. The drug's size is an important consideration. Drugs have a hard time penetrating the thick extracellular matrix. On the other hand, tumor-induced angiogenesis hindered lymphatic drainage and encouraged the formation of many immature vasculatures. Due to the "leaky" nature of these juvenile vasculatures, nanoparticles can easily enter the target areas. The good surface to volume ratio of PNPs makes it convenient to affix targeting peptides to their surface. The surfactant action of polysorbates can facilitate fluidization and solubilization. Polysorbate coating of polymers can increase

bioavailability and enhance PNP-endothelial interaction. The surfactant action of polysorbates can facilitate fluidization and solubilization. Enhancing the bioavailability of polymers by coating them with polysorbates can encourage PNPs to interact with blood-brain barrier endothelial cell membranes and facilitate endocytosis. PNPs has the ability to react to ultrasound and deliver anticancer medications to target locations more effectively than conventional chemical treatments. Fluorescent PNPs are essential to theragnostics, a unique approach that combines diagnosis and treatment. Fluorescent PNPs with intricate structures have been employed as theragnostic materials in recent years. Organic dyes, fluorescent proteins, and biocompatible biopolymers are commonly used to create fluorescent PNPs. Furthermore, fluorescence experiments indicate that hydrophobic interactions or π - π bonds enhance the anticancer effect of nanomedicine. I-125 and other radionuclides can be kept in the steady core through the electrophilic replacement of aromatic nanoparticles. Additionally, an 11 nm self-assembling protein nanoparticle was created, and it demonstrated stability and biocompatibility in vivo, indicating its potential for use in cancer therapy drug delivery. PNPs that are sensitive to ultrasound are useful for treating and diagnosing cancer. By overcoming "obstacles" (such as endothelial blood arteries, tissue endothelium, and the blood-brain barrier) connected with the traversing ability of cancer treatments, ultrasound was used in the production of nanoparticles to lessen side effects and improve drug delivery. Chemical medications can be released under controlled conditions using ultrasound, which exhibits a thermal effect. Still needing to be improved upon in terms of manufacturing and characteristics are some degraded PNPs that are poisonous. steady core through the electrophilic replacement of aromatic nanoparticles (42, 43). Additionally,

an 11 nm self-assembling protein nanoparticle was created, and it demonstrated stability and biocompatibility *in vivo*, indicating its potential for use in cancer therapy drug delivery (44). PNPs that are sensitive to ultrasound are useful for treating and diagnosing cancer. By overcoming "obstacles" (such as endothelial blood arteries, tissue endothelium, and the blood-brain barrier) connected with the traversing ability of cancer

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Figure 2: Nanomaterials-based cancer therapeutic methods. (A) Using active or passive targeting to attack cancer cells. (B) Targeting TME, including extracellular matrix, stromal cells, and anti-angiogenesis. To inhibit angiogenesis, bevacizumab was coupled with VEGF and put into liposomes. The NP surface was coated with HAase, increasing the NP's capacity to penetrate. c In cancer immunotherapy, IFN- γ as an immune regulator supplied by liposomes stimulated immune cells. NP stands for nanoparticle; TME stands for tumor microenvironment; HAase stands for hyaluronidase; and VEGF stands for vascular endothelial growth factor

Nano particle monoclonal antibodies
Monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) are extensively employed in targeted treatment due to their anticancer effect and particular targeting

capabilities. mAbs have been employed as front-runners in the fight against cancer and in anticancer nanoplatforms more recently. Antibody-drug conjugates, also referred to as cytotoxic medications coupled with mAbs, enhance the anticancer drug's therapeutic efficacy. Less toxicity and greater specificity can be obtained based on the particular antigens expressed in cancer cells . In breast cancer, many antibody-drug conjugate systems show improved therapeutic efficacy .Trastuzumab nanoparticles are a promising and extensively researched nanoplatform for cancer treatment, based on the effects of antibody-drug conjugates .

Lipid-Oriented Nanostructures Lipid-based nanomaterials can be broadly classified into three types: liposomes, solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs), and nanostructured lipid carriers. As the first

microcosmic phospholipid bilayer nanosystem, liposomes ranged in size from 20 nm to >1 μm . Depending on the liposome structure, medicines that are hydrophilic or hydrophobic can be administered. The liposomes' interior chamber prevents drugs from degrading. Human guards, a mononuclear phagocyte system, have the potential to phagocytize liposomes; thus, liposome membranes ought to be altered to extend their half-life. The conjugation of polyethylene glycol can do this. For instance, doxorubicin (DOX)-loaded PEG-liposomes were created and used to treat Kaposi sarcoma. Liposomes have been paired with chemical medications and are frequently used in co-delivery and controlled release scenarios. How to fill prescriptions reduced bioavailability compared to free DOX, indicating that liposome design should enhance bioavailability. A novel PEGylated liposome containing ncl-240 and cobimetinib demonstrated increased cytotoxicity due to synergistic actions, resulting in increased effectiveness. Furthermore, advanced solid tumors responded better to liposomes loaded with floxuridine and irinotecan, whereas a novel liposome incorporating multilayer siRNA molecules and co-delivered DOX demonstrated improved DOX efficacy, reducing the tumor bulk in breast cancer. Notably, because malignant areas are more acidic than healthy tissues, certain liposomes can release medications based on the pH level. A pH-sensitive substance was used to create pH-sensitive cationic liposomes. At pH 6.5, sorafenib released more readily. To sum up, liposomes show minimal cytotoxicity, minimal immunogenicity, and plus excellent biodegradability. Liposomes' low stability, difficulties transferring membranes, and quick elimination by the mononuclear phagocyte system are among its drawbacks. As a result, liposome applications are still restricted. SLNs have been used as liposome substitute carriers. When compared to other larger

nanoparticles, SLNs (1–100 nm) are referred to as "zero-dimensional" nanomaterials due to the strict confinement of the scale. Unlike liposomes, solid components are present in SLNs. Emulsifiers, water, and solid lipids are a few examples of these substances. Triglycerides, fatty acids, and PEGylated lipids are used in SLNs. While SLNs' outer layer and distribution mechanism are comparable to those of normal liposomes, there are some notable variations. Some SLNs contain pharmaceuticals encapsulated in the core of a micelle-like structure instead of a continuous bilayer... SLNs exhibit longer release times and greater stability when compared to liposomes. SLNs do, however, have certain drawbacks due to their crystalline structure, including intrinsically low integration rates and an erratic gelation tendency. To address the shortcomings of SLNs, nanostructured lipid carriers, or NLCs, have been created. They are also known as the second lifetime of lipid nanoparticles. NLCs have a greater loading capacity and a lower gelation inclination than SLNs. Because many medications used in cancer therapy are lipophilic and can be delivered orally, parenterally, inhaled, or through the eyes, NLCs have drawn a lot of interest recently. Systems that convey both liquid and solid lipids are used in the manufacturing of NLCs. In the previous 20 years, NLCs' stability and loading capacity have changed throughout time.

Nanobots: Primary Trials And Its Mechanism

Researchers at Harvard University's Wyss Institute put fluorescently tagged antibodies against human leukocyte antigens into the nanobots to specifically bind to the cancer cells. Upon The bots would deliver the payload after identifying the target proteins. Administers and carries the medication. Amir et al. introduced different nanobots into cockroaches later in 2014. (*Blaberus discoidalis*) in order to observe how they

target and distribute the medication. Fluorescent markers were used to identify each nanobot, and the Researchers pursued them in order to examine where and how they delivered the medication. According to Bachelet, the accuracy and management of the Bots functioned similarly to computer systems, and this was the first after biological treatment has paralleled the functioning of a computer processor [45]. Unlike the existing nanobots, these ones are cell-specific. When it comes to poorly focused medicines, these bots will be an advanced advancement in the management of cancer. But a course of treatment such as this in Humans have to overcome their bodies' immunological responses. Bachelet is ensure that the nanobots can be stabilized in order for the body to sustain them. Lately, California Institute of Technology researchers have constructed nanobots that may distribute and sort the medication. There are three components to the bot. components: a "leg," a "hand," and a "arm" that

Nanobots in Medicine: Current Applications

The role of nanobots in various medical scenarios is under close examination in pursuit of unlocking their full potential. Currently, the main medical fields where nanobots are applied are disease diagnosis, treatment, drug delivery, and surgery. As technology and healthcare software development advances, the use of nanobots in medicine could transform cancer care, diabetes management, wound healing, and dental care, among other areas. So, let's see how they make a difference in healthcare today. Medical nanobots can be used in diagnosis, monitoring and treating critical diseases. These are capable of delivering medicine into the specific target site in human body. The potential applications of nanobots include.

Drug Delivery Systems

Imagine that medication goes exactly where it's needed without affecting healthy cells—this is the groundbreaking promise of medical nanorobots. Traditional drug delivery methods often have side effects, as they can't distinguish between sick and healthy cells. Nanobots change the game by delivering drugs with laser-like precision. Here's how it works: nanorobots are programmed to recognize specific markers of diseased cells. Once they find their target, they release the medication directly into the affected cells. This not only maximizes the drug's impact but also minimizes harm to healthy tissues. In essence, nanobots medicine offers a smarter, more efficient way to treat diseases, from cancer to chronic conditions. It's like having a GPS that guides your medicine straight to the sick parts.

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Diagnostic Procedures

The advantages of nanobots in medicine for diagnosis are immense, particularly in the early detection of life-threatening diseases like cancer and heart disease. A simple injection of nanorobots could roam your body, seeking out early signs of trouble long before symptoms appear.

How? Software engineers program these nanobots to identify abnormal cells or markers in the bloodstream. For instance, in the case of cancer, they can detect tumor cells at a very early stage, allowing for prompt and more effective treatment.

In heart disease, they can identify plaque buildup in arteries before it becomes a significant issue.

Surgery and Repair

Nanorobotics can give surgeons an extra hand during complex operations, making the whole process faster, less painful, and more affordable. They're good at specific jobs like taking out harmful stuff or getting medication exactly where it needs to go. With nanobots helping out, there's a lower chance of something going wrong during the surgery, which means fewer repeat operations. As for tissue repair and regeneration, nanobots can speed up the healing process by half or more by delivering specialized substances that help tissues grow back faster and more efficiently. It means less time for healing and a quicker return to normal life. For instance, NanoScientifica invested years in developing nanobots that operate at a breakneck speed, far outpacing conventional treatments. Yes, this is the future that nanobots' medical applications can offer to modern healthcare.

Gene Therapy

Once a concept described in science fiction, it's now a thriving field in medicine, with nanobots at the forefront of this revolution. Researchers employ them to tackle genetic diseases at their very root—our DNA. Soon, with the help of nanorobots, healthcare professionals can treat inherited diseases like cystic fibrosis or muscular dystrophy in a radically new way. Instead of just managing symptoms, these tiny mechanisms can correct underlying genetic flaws.

Nanobots in researching medicine are showing promise in delivering gene-editing tools like CRISPR directly to the affected cells. By doing so,

they can replace or repair the faulty genes, essentially rewriting the script of life. While the full potential of this technology is still under exploration, early studies are encouraging. For example, researchers at the University of California, San Diego, experimented with nanobots that can deliver a payload of gene-editing tools to treat genetic blood disorders. The implications are breathtaking. Using nanobots medical solutions in gene therapy could mean more effective treatments, fewer side effects, and even a win over certain genetic diseases.

Smart Vaccination

Powered by nanorobotics, smart vaccination can boost the human immune system. Take, for example, the Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 vaccine, which employs iron nanoparticles to transport RNA molecules into our bodies. These nanoparticles target only our white blood cells. Once there, the cells produce proteins mimicking the coronavirus' spikes, enabling them to recognize and neutralize the virus more effectively. Thus, nanobot in medicine application equips our immune system to combat virus mutations more effectively, providing a level of protection that traditional vaccines can't match. Integrating nanotechnology into vaccination protocols could mark a paradigm shift in public health, offering more robust and long-lasting immunity.

Hematology:

Nanobots have potential application in the field of hematology. Its use in hematology ranges from emergency transfusions of non-blood oxygen carrying compounds to restoring primary hemostasis (Saadeh and Vyas, 2014) Respirocytes are spherical 1 μm diameter sized nanobots which are designed as artificial mechanical red blood cells. The respirocyte could deliver 236 times more oxygen to the body tissue when compared to natural red blood cells. The respirocyte would manage the carbonic acidity that can be controlled

by gas concentration sensors and on-board nanocomputer (Freitas, 2005a) Each respirocyte has 3 types of rotors. One rotor releases the stored oxygen while travelling through the body. The second rotor captures all the carbon dioxide at blood stream and releases at the lungs. The third rotor takes glucose from blood stream and uses as fuel source (Mishra and Dash, 2012). It can be programmed to scavenge carbon monoxide and other poisonous gases from the body. A 5 cc therapeutic dose of 50% respirocyte saline suspension contains 5 trillion nanorobots that could exactly replace the gas carrying capacity of the patient's entire 5.4 litres of blood (Freitas, 2005b). Microbivores are the nanobots that are designed as artificial WBC and also known as nanobotic phagocytes. It is a spheroid device made of diamond and sapphire which measures 3.4 μm in diameter along its major axis and 2 μm diameter along its minor axis. Microbivore absorbs and digests the pathogens in the blood stream by the process of phagocytosis (Eshaghian-Wilner, 2009). During the cycle of operation, the target bacterium binds to the microbivore surface via specific reversible binding site. A collision between the bacterium and microbivore brings in the surface into close contact and thus the reversible binding site can be recognized and weakly bound to the bacterium. When the bacterium is bound to the binding site, the telescopic robotic grapples rise up from the surface and attach to the bacterium. Then the bacterium is transported from the binding site to the injection port by the grapple's handoff motion. Then the bacterium is internalized into the morcellation chamber where the bacterium is minced into nanoscale pieces. These pieces of bacterium are pistoned into digestive chamber which consists of pre-programmed set of digestive enzymes. Then it is converted into amino acids, mononucleotides, free fatty acids and simple sugars which are then discharged into blood stream through the exhaust

port. It needs 30 seconds to complete the entire cycle of phagocytosis by microbivore (Manjunath and Kishore, 2014). Microbivore acts 1000 times faster than antibiotic aided WBCs and the pathogen stand no chance of multiple drug resistance which occurs in case of antibiotic. They can also be used in case of respiratory and cerebrospinal bacterial infection or infection in urinary fluid and synovial fluid (Eshaghian-Wilner, 2009)

Cancer detection and treatment:

Cancer can be successfully diagnosed and treated with the help of nanobots. Unlike the conventional drug, nanobots are highly site specific i.e. it is programmed to detect only the diseased cells to act upon them, the healthy cells are left aside and thus show minimum side effects. Nanobots with embedded biosensors can be used in detection of tumor cells in the early stage of development inside the patient's body (Sivasankar and Durairaj, 2012). Kumar et al. (2014) has reported that, scientists have genetically modified salmonella bacteria carrying microscopic robots (3 μm) named bacteriobots, which are drawn to tumors by chemicals secreted by the cancerous cells. These deliver drug directly to the tumor leaving the healthy cells alone and thus protect the patient from side effects of chemotherapy. But these bacteriobot can only detect the tumor in case of breast cancer and colorectal cancers. On the contrary, nanobot is able to detect and treat other cancers (Kumar et al., 2014)

Implications and Future Directions

Nanoparticles provide opportunities for designing and tuning properties that are not possible with other types of therapeutic drugs, and have shown a bright future as a new generation of cancer therapeutics. Furthermore, the development of multifunctional nanoparticles may eventually render nanoparticles able to detect and kill cancer cells simultaneously. Although there are certain critical questions and many challenges remaining for the clinical development of nanoparticles, as more clinical data are available, further understanding in nanotechnology will certainly lead to the more rational design of optimized nanoparticles with improved selectivity, efficacy, and safety

CONCLUSION

When utilized as circuits, DNA has been employed to store data and amplify signals, but these applications pale in comparison to the advantages of the bots [45]. Due to their specialized actions and lack of impact on nearby healthy cells, these bots are ideal for controlled medication release and targeted drug therapy. In medical research, nanotechnology will be a breakthrough if the study is successful. It is possible to avoid side effects if this technology is used in place of the existing treatments. Researchers are also experimenting with acoustic communication between nanobots to help them coordinate and act on a particular location [57]. At present, it is believed that the nanobots can treat cancer completely within a month. In the future, with more improvements, it can be used to cure cancer within a few days or even a few hours, no matter how far the disease has spread. On further research, it can be used even to defend people who have chances of getting cancer, prevent cancers which are hereditary, or where cancer is a sure possibility (like victims of liver cirrhosis). Scientists are to produce increasingly more complex nanomachines such as red blood cells 2.0

(synthetic particles that are like real red blood cells and can stay longer in the body), microbivores (nanobots capable of destroying pathogens inside the body) [58] and nanobots which suck up ocean pollution [59]. Although they are still in the research and development phase, their potential is innumerable. Additionally, nanotechnology can be utilized to create smart bandages that promote faster wound healing [60].

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